

Oblique extension favours propagation pulses during continental break-up

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Introduction

This supplementary information file contains additional models results.

Figure S1 shows the β factor of the crust computed as

$$\beta = \frac{h_c^{t=0}}{h_c^{t=n}} \quad (10)$$

where $h_c^{t=0}$ is the initial thickness of the crust at the beginning of the simulation ($h_c = 40$ km, $t = 0$ Myr) and $h_c^{t=n}$ is the thickness of the crust at a given time n . Thus, the β factor value represents the thinning ratio of the crust at a given time.

Figures S2, S5 and S8 show the strain regime. The strain regime is computed from the components of the stress tensor and is known as the Regime Stress Ratio (RSR, (Brune, 2014; Brune & Autin, 2013). A detailed procedure to compute is available in Brune (2014).

Brune, S. (2014). Evolution of stress and fault patterns in oblique rift systems: 3-D numerical lithospheric-scale experiments from rift to breakup. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*, 15, 3392–3415.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/2014GC005446>. Received

Brune, S., & Autin, J. (2013). The rift to break-up evolution of the Gulf of Aden: Insights from 3D numerical lithospheric-scale modelling. *Tectonophysics*, 607, 65–79.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tecto.2013.06.029>

Figure S1. Map view of nine models with a strong and weak lower crust and varying v_z velocities of the crustal beta factor. Thin dotted lines represent isovalues of beta factor spaced every 0.2.

Weak Lower Crust
 $V_z = 1.2$ mm/yr (model 1)

Figure S2. Numerical model with a weak lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.2 mm/yr. Left panels show a map view evolution of the strain regime. Background colours correspond to the simulated lithologies presented in Figure 3. Red dashed lines shows the locations of cross-sections displayed in the right panels.

Weak Lower Crust
 $V_z = 1.2 \text{ mm/yr}$

Figure S3. Numerical model with a weak lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.2 mm/yr. Left panels show a map view evolution of the plastic strain (deformation related to equation 6) in the crust and exhumation ages of the mantle below the 800°C isotherm. Red dashed lines shows the locations of cross-sections displayed in the right panels (viscous deformation is related to equation 7).

Weak Lower Crust
 $V_z = 1.2 \text{ mm/a}$

Figure S4. Numerical model with a weak lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.2 mm/yr . Left panels show a map view evolution of the absolute surface velocity field. Right panels show a map view evolution of the beta factor.

Weak Lower Crust
 $V_z = 1.5 \text{ mm/yr}$

Figure S5. Numerical model with a weak lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.5 mm/yr. Left panels show a map view evolution of the strain regime. Background colours correspond to the simulated lithologies presented in Figure 3. Red dashed lines shows the locations of cross-sections displayed in the right panels.

Weak Lower Crust

$V_z = 1.5 \text{ mm/yr}$

Figure S6. Numerical model with a weak lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.5 mm/yr . Left panels show a map view evolution of the plastic strain (deformation related to equation 6) in the crust and exhumation ages of the mantle below the 800°C isotherm. Red dashed lines shows the locations of cross-sections displayed in the right panels (viscous deformation is related to equation 7).

Weak Lower Crust

$V_z = 1.5 \text{ mm/a}$

Figure S7. Numerical model with a weak lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.5 mm/yr. Left panels show a map view evolution of the absolute surface velocity field. Right panels show a map view evolution of the beta factor.

Strong Lower Crust
 $V_z = 1.7 \text{ mm/yr}$ (model 3)

Figure S8. Numerical model with a strong lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.7 mm/yr. Left panels show a map view evolution of the strain regime.

Background colours correspond to the simulated lithologies presented in Figure 3. Red dashed lines shows the locations of cross-sections displayed in the right panels.

Strong Lower Crust
 $V_z = 1.7 \text{ mm/yr}$

Figure S9. Numerical model with a strong lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.7 mm/yr. Left panels show a map view evolution of the plastic strain (deformation related to equation 6) in the crust and exhumation ages of the mantle below the 800°C isotherm. Red dashed lines shows the locations of cross-sections displayed in the right panels (viscous deformation is related to equation 7).

Strong Lower Crust

$V_z = 1.7 \text{ mm/a}$

Figure S10. Numerical model with a strong lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.7 mm/yr . Left panels show a map view evolution of the absolute surface velocity field. Right panels show a map view evolution of the beta factor.

Figure S11. Numerical model with a strong lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.2 mm/yr

Figure S12. Numerical model with a weak lower crust and a v_z shortening velocity of 1.7 mm/yr